

IPBES TCA Chapter 2. DMR 2.11 Content analysis of most inspiring visions / IPBES transformative change assessment

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Description: The review corresponds to the IPBES transformative change assessment. The IPBES Scoping document for the transformative change assessment describes that chapter 2 should consider the implications of different visions for sectors, subsystems (including market/economic, financial, political, legal/judicial, educational, indigenous and local systems, and ecosystems) and interactions between these, at a variety of spatial scales.

In this context, in addition to the descriptive and cluster analyses of coded visions, a content analysis of most inspiring visions from each of the subtopic or content areas was performed. Such an approach allowed to identify and analyze the content, focus and values underlying the visions, as well as the direct and indirect drivers of biodiversity loss identified.

Then another qualitative assessment framework was developed to further analyze the most inspiring visions, in particular to visualize 1) their overall transformative potential and, 2) how their underlying nature's values were aligned with the Nature Futures Framework.

Process overview

Protocol

Step1 - Selection and initial content analysis of most potentially transformative visions

Method: Each coder was requested to submit an initial set of three to five descriptions and sources of the most potentially transformative visions (most inspiring visions) from within their categories, using either a single source or combined sources that constitute a vision.

Coders were asked to provide a rating (from 1 to 3) along multiple criteria drawn from the quality criteria for visions identified by Wiek & Iwaniec (2014), and prior documents and works on biodiversity and ecosystem services including the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD), the 2050 Vision for Biodiversity, and IPBES (2019).

Table A summarizes these assessment criteria, which included the extent to which biodiversity was discussed. It also included core criteria for assessing transformative potential drawn from Wiek & Iwaniec (2014): transformative, systematic, plausible, tangible, relevant, motivational, and inclusive.

In addition, coders were asked to evaluate the extent to which the following topics were included: topics from the *Nexus Assessment* (food, water, health); changes in views and values, actions, and structures (framework defined by chapter 1); and pathways forward (to inform chapter 5). Coders were also asked to provide short descriptions of each of these aspects as well as synthetic descriptions of the submitted visions.

Table A. table for coder-selected most potentially transformative visions

Dear author, for each selected vision:

-> Please provide a synthetic description (max. 1 page).

-> Please fill in this table (see relevant definitions and criteria below).

		Rating*	Comment (Please add a description for each item)
Quality criteria	Biodiversity		
	Transformative		
	Systematic		
	Plausible		
	Tangible		
	Relevant		
	Motivational		
	Inclusive		
Nexus topics	Food		
	Water		
	Health		
Ch 1 Framework	Views and values+		
	Actions++		
	Structures+++		
Ch 5	Pathways++++		

Definition of Vision: Visions are descriptions of desirable future states of nature and people. As such, they embody purpose/goals and are shaped by values. Visions can result from different processes, including –

but not limited to – visioning. All have the potential to enable transformative Change. They can 'happen' or not, but they prepare us for these desirable future states. They gain power if they are widely shared. The visions can be explicit or implicit in the sources. Both can be included in the selection. However, for implicit visions the description of the desirable future state of nature and people needs to be extracted. One vision can be extracted from a single source or collated from several sources. The source(s) of the vision should be indicated.

***Rating:** 3=most/highest; 2=modest/some/adequate; 1=least/lowest

+Definition of views and values (Ch1): *What We Think and Feel*. This dimension includes, for example, how we see the world and our place within it, as well as what we value and prioritize.

++Definition of actions (Ch1): *What We Do*. This dimension includes, for example, our behaviours and practices at both individual and collective levels.

+++ Definition of structures (Ch1): *The Things That Influence How We Think, Feel and Act*. This dimension includes, for example, laws, institutions, norms, policies, regulatory frameworks, organizations, etc. Structures are, across all positions, framed as being inseparable from actions, and views and values. Structures are the framework that allow power and economy/capitalism to be expressed.

++++ Definition of Pathways (Ch5): they are descriptions of the temporal evolution of specific scenario aspects, representing different strategies for moving from a business-as-usual situation towards a desired future vision for a sustainable world.

Step 2 – Development of a qualitative content analysis framework

Method: While the set of most potentially transformative visions was being finalized, the content analysis team of three coders reviewed initial descriptions and developed a framework that after several revisions included the following categories:

- Main purpose or goal of the vision.
- The ‘what’ of the vision, that is, a description of the desirable future for nature and people that is envisioned.
- The broad values, or general moral guiding principles, explicitly or implicitly expressed in the vision (broadly linked to ‘views and values’ as defined by chapter 1).
- The specific values related to nature, explicitly or implicitly expressed by the vision, which were designated in three categories as outlined by the Nature Futures Framework and related sources: *instrumental* (nature as a means to achieve or satisfy human needs), *intrinsic* (nature is valuable in-and-of itself regardless of its usefulness to people), *relational* (nature's value stems from meaningful, often reciprocal people-nature relations and people-people relations through nature).
- Direct drivers as defined by IPBES: both human and non-human induced changes that affect nature directly, including land-use change, sea use, climate change, pollution, natural resources use and exploitation, and invasive species, designations broadly linked to both actions and power items discussed in chapter 1.
- Indirect drivers: human actions and decisions that affect nature by influencing direct drivers, including demographic, technological, economics, and governance factors. They were considered to be broadly linked to actions, structures, and power as discussed in chapter 1.
- Open coding: a category that provides for inclusion of relevant information emerging from the data and not included elsewhere.

- In addition, a note was included as to whether the original source material needed to be consulted in order to flesh out relevant details of a given vision description.

Table B summarizes the qualitative content analysis framework. The complete content analysis framework with definitions and sources can be found in:

3-IPBES_TCA_CH2_DMR 2.11_MTV_content analysis framework(A)

Table B: Qualitative Content Analysis Framework (summary)

	Comment or Description from vision (<100 words)
Vision Id and Name (if available)	
Is there enough information in the description/template or should the source(s) be consulted?	
Main Purpose or Goal	
The 'What'	
Broad Values	
Specific Values of Nature <i>Instrumental values</i> <i>Intrinsic values</i> <i>Relational values</i>	
Direct Drivers <i>land-use change, sea use, climate change, pollution, natural resource use and exploitation, invasive species (as per coding spreadsheet).</i>	
Indirect Drivers (Actions, structures, power shifts) <i>Indirect drivers: include demographic, technological, economic and governance (as per coding spreadsheet).</i>	
Open coding	

Step 3 – Content analysis of most potentially transformative visions

Description: The most potentially transformative visions submitted by the coders were then collected into a single document to facilitate content analysis by a team of three coders. The content was analyzed with the qualitative content analysis framework shown in table B.

Step 4 – Analysis of visions' transformative potential and underlying nature's values

Description: Another qualitative content analysis framework was developed to assess 1) the overall transformative potential of the selected visions and, 2) how the values underlying the selected visions were aligned with the Nature Futures Framework (Pereira et al., 2020; Durán et al., 2023). A summary of the content analysis framework is included as table C. The complete content analysis framework with more detailed definitions and sources can be found in:

5-IPBES_TCA_CH2_DMR 2.15_MTV_analysis transformative potential and values(C)

Table C. Framework to assess the transformative potential and nature's values of most potentially transformative visions (summary)

Vision name	Resistance from the status quo	Comprehensiveness	Specific nature value orientation	Real world example
Provide a short name for the vision.	Assess how likely the implementation of the vision is to encounter resistance from the status quo, i.e., powerful actors in the relevant (sub-)system opposing transformative change.	Assess the extent to which the vision targets both sustainability and equity; it addresses indirect drivers; it entails a change in views (what we think and feel), actions (what we do), structures and institutions (the things that influence how we think, feel and act); and it rearranges power relations.	Assign the vision to one of the seven areas of the NFF triangle: 1) almost exclusively relational; 2) almost exclusively intrinsic; 3) almost exclusively instrumental; 4) between relational and intrinsic without instrumental component; 5) between intrinsic and instrumental without relational component; 6) between relational and instrumental without intrinsic component; 7) balance between relational, intrinsic, and instrumental.	If you know of any example where this vision has inspired transformative change, please explain where, how, by whom, positive/negative effects, etc. Focus on resistance and comprehensiveness with the audience of policymakers in mind.

Sub step 4.1 – Transformative potential

Method: To determine the transformative potential of the visions, each selected vision was assessed along two dimensions using the guidance developed in table C (see figure 2.5A of chapter 2). On the vertical axis was the overall resistance that the implementation of the vision is likely to encounter from powerful actors of the status quo. This assessment holistically combined a number of criteria for transformative quality of visions developed by Wiek and Iwaniec (2014), including plausibility, tangibility, relevance, and motivational potential. On the horizontal axis the comprehensiveness of each vision was assessed, using the assumption that more comprehensive or holistic visions are needed to achieve sustainability and equity, the overall goals of systemic change as identified in the transformative change assessment. To accomplish this, the general framework developed by chapter 1 was used. In particular, the assessment focused on the extent to which the vision, if implemented, would require changes in views and values, actions, structures, institutions, and power relations, as well as the extent to which the vision addresses indirect drivers of biodiversity loss. These two dimensions (resistance to change and comprehensiveness) were considered to shape the transformative potential of a vision.

One coder provided a preliminary assessment of each of the visions using these criteria, which was then supplemented by the assessment of two other coders especially where initial differences existed. Since coders sometimes differed in their assessments, all three coders then discussed each of the criteria with respect to the visions to come to a consensus about how that vision should be ranked and where it should be placed in the figure.

Each vision was assigned a number from 1 (low) to 10 (high) and placed in the figure. This assessment resulted in a four-quadrant figure. The lower left quadrant contains visions

encountering high resistance and having low comprehensiveness, while the upper left quadrant contains visions encountering low resistance and having low comprehensiveness. The lower right quadrant represents high resistance combined with high comprehensiveness, while the upper right quadrant represents low resistance combined with high comprehensiveness. The latter quadrant is where the visions have the maximum transformative potential.

Sub step 4.2 - Nature's values

Method: A similar process was followed to determine which values of nature were dominant in each of the visions. The values of nature associated with each most potentially transformative vision were assessed in relation to how they fit in the Nature Futures Framework generated and used by IPBES (Pereira et al., 2020; Durán et al., 2023). The Nature Futures Framework is developed as a triangle with each of its three corners representing a core perspective on how humans relate to nature: *Nature for Nature*, which relates to intrinsically valuing nature in and of itself, *Nature for Society*, which emphasizes instrumental values focused on the way nature provides benefits for people, and *Nature as Culture*, which emphasizes values stemming from the relationships between people and nature (Pereira et al., 2020; IPBES, 2022). While these values are located at the corners of the NFF triangle, many visions evidence elements of more than one value orientation. Visions that evidence little or no concern for nature would fall outside of the triangle.

The selected visions were classified into seven possible value orientations with the NFF triangle as a reference, following the template developed in table C: almost exclusively relational; almost exclusively intrinsic; almost exclusively instrumental; between relational and intrinsic without instrumental component; between intrinsic and instrumental without relational component; between relational and instrumental without intrinsic component; balance between relational, intrinsic, and instrumental. The location of these value orientations in the NFF triangle can be seen in Figure 2.5B of chapter 2. The assessment followed the process described above for assessing the visions' transformative potential, i.e., the three coders provided assessments which were discussed against the criteria specified in table C to come to a consensus about the value orientation of each vision.

After sub steps 4.1 and 4.2, the database was cleansed by removing records containing dystopian elements, records with insufficient information to properly characterize a vision, and records lacking reference to nature/biodiversity. The outcome of sub step 4.1 is presented as Figure 2.5A of chapter 2. The outcome of sub step 4.2 is presented as Figure 2.5B of chapter 2.

Step 5 – Gap filling for “Nature for Nature” value orientation

Method: After the internal review of the Second Order Draft, reviewers pointed out the need to find visions in the Nature for Nature (intrinsic value of nature) corner of the NFF. Hence, expert knowledge from the Chapter 2 team was used to identify potentially transformative visions that valued nature intrinsically. Five visions were selected. These visions were then assessed using the same procedure explained in sub steps 4.1 and 4.2. These five visions were included in figure 2.5B but not in figure 2.5A.

Location and description of the data: The final datasets resulting from the analyses detailed in this DMR can be found in:

4-IPBES_TCA_CH2_DMR 2.11_MTV_content_analysis(B)

5-IPBES_TCA_CH2_DMR 2.15_MTV_analysis transformative potential and values(C).

References

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Definition of files

	name	content	type
1	1-IPBES_TCA_CH2_DMR 2.11_most_transformative_visions.pdf	DMR	.pdf
2	2-IPBES_TCA_CH2_DMR 2.11_MTV_process.jpeg	Flowchart of the process	.jpeg
3	3-IPBES_TCA_CH2_DMR 2.11_MTV_content_analysis_framework(A)	Qualitative content analysis framework	.pdf
4	4-IPBES_TCA_CH2_DMR 2.11_MTV_content_analysis(B)	Initial content analysis	pdf
5	5-IPBES_TCA_CH2_DMR 2.15_MTV_analysis_transf_potential&values(C)	Transformative potential and NFF analysis	pdf